

1 **HIV-1 Vpr activates Cxcl8.**

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6 The HIV-1 genome consists of 9 genes: Gag, Pol and Env, regulatory genes Tat and Rev, and the
7 accessory genes Nef, Vif, Vpr and Vpu. To study Vpr function in an unbiased fashion, we measured total
8 transcription in human U2OS cells following transduction with Vpr. Cells robustly activated Cxcl8 in
9 response to Vpr expression. Cxcl8 production in response to Vpr expression was specific because cells
10 expressing three separate Vpr point mutants, Vpr S79A, Vpr H71R and Vpr Q65R were completely
11 defective in Cxcl8 production. HIV-1 Vpr activates Cxcl8.

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13 Citations

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